

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 150

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 150

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 150:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! Praise God in His ^asanctuary; Praise Him in His mighty ^{3b}expanse. ² Praise Him for His ^amighty deeds; Praise Him according to His excellent ^bgreatness.</p> <p>Psa. 150:3 Praise Him with ^atrumpet sound; Praise Him with ^bharp and lyre. ⁴ Praise Him with ^atimbrel and dancing; Praise Him with ^bstringed instruments and ^cpipe. ⁵ Praise Him with loud ^acymbals; Praise Him with resounding cymbals. ⁶ Let ^aeverything that has breath praise ¹the LORD. ²Praise ¹the LORD!</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Psa. 150:1</p> <p>הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי-שָׁמַיִם בְּקֹדֶשׁוֹ הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּרָקִיעַ עֲלֹן : ² הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּגִבּוֹרֹתָיו הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה כְּרֹב גְּדֻלָּתוֹ : ³ הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּתַקְעַת שׁוֹפָר הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּנִבְל וְכִנּוֹר : ⁴ הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּתֹרָה וּמְחֹל הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּמִנְיִים וְעוּגָב : ⁵ הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּצִלְצְלֵי-שָׁמַע הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה בְּצִלְצְלֵי תְרוּעָה : ⁶ כָּל הַנְּשָׁמָה תְהַלֵּל יְהוָה הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה :</p>

References

Psalm 150:1

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

³Or *firmament*

^aPs 73:17; 102:19

^bPs 19:1

Psalm 150:2

^aPs 145:12

^bDeut 3:24; Ps 145:3

Psalm 150:3

^aPs 98:6

^bPs 33:2

Psalm 150:4

^aPs 149:3

^bPs 45:8; Is 38:20

^cGen 4:21; Job 21:12

Psalm 150:5

^a2 Sam 6:5; 1 Chr 13:8; 15:16; Ezra 3:10; Neh 12:27

Psalm 150:6

¹Heb *YAH*

²Or *Hallelujah!*

^aPs 103:22; 145:21

Targum

Psa. 150:1 Hallelujah! Praise God in his sanctuary, praise him in the firmament of his strength. ² Praise him for his mighty deeds, praise him according to his abundant greatness. ³ Praise him with the sounding of the trumpet, praise him with harps and lyres. ⁴ Praise him with drums and with dances, praise him with flutes and pipes. ⁵ Praise him with cymbals that sound alone; praise him with cymbals that sound with shouting. ⁶ Every breath will sing praise to God. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm summarizes the Book of Psalms.

Notes on this Psalm

The development of the spiritual is the most important a person does during their lifetime. The Zohar says that the soul is sent to Malkut and joined with flesh to learn about the LORD. 1/5th of the soul is the flesh. It is a fight between materialism and spiritualism that life is all about. Remember that one day you will return to the Lower Waters. Will you be ready?

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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